

Engaging Asia's Hobgoblin:

Japanese Diplomacy and the Democratic People's Republic of Korea

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Abstract

The Democratic People's Republic of Korea (DPRK) is seen as a significant security threat and, alongside the state's history of provocative actions and poor human rights record, this has made it a virtual pariah, economically isolated by a crippling sanctions regime. In the face of recent diplomatic initiatives with the DPRK, Japan has encountered pressure from its US ally to maintain a more hardline approach by continuing to focus on prioritization of the DPRK as a serious security threat. Such a stance would hamper diplomatic rapprochement and, by sustaining the economic status quo, increase the chances of a governmental collapse within the DPRK. Analysis of the current situation suggests that such destabilization would present a far greater danger to Japan's security than the alternative. Namely, downgrading the military threat posed by the DPRK and instead focusing on the reform of its economic and human rights problems as a means of encouraging compliance with international norms.

Keywords:

Japan, North Korea, DPRK, nuclear weapons, abduction.

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INTRODUCTION

The American social critic H.L. Mencken famously described democracy an amalgam of competing fears in which the primary aim of politics was “to keep the populace alarmed, and hence clamorous to be led to safety, by menacing it with an endless series of hobgoblins, most of them imaginary”.¹⁾ In an age of bird flu and ebola, Al Qaeda and ISIS, sources of such alarm are far from lacking, yet in Asia one stands above all others as a constant generator of fear, insecurity and paranoid militarization. The Democratic People’s Republic of Korea (DPRK) has been described variously as a ‘hermit kingdom’, ‘rogue state’, ‘terrorist sponsor’ and ‘brutal prison’, and remains the most politically isolated country in the world.²⁾ For decades it has served to promote tension and insecurity in not only its neighboring states but the entire global community through the unresolved nature of its war with South Korea, overt focus on military growth, hyperbolic threats, restrictive human rights record, abduction of foreign citizens and development of ballistic missile technology and nuclear weapons.

As a result, most academic analysis of the DPRK’s role in regional affairs has focused on the need for a steadfast response to the state’s misconduct. Fontaine and Springut, for example, address the common trifecta of diplomatic efforts to encourage denuclearization, the need for a possible military response and provisions for a sudden collapse of government.³⁾ Kaplan sees China as playing a key role in hampering these moves by “propping up the DPRK, forgiving or overlooking its many sins, and preventing the United States and the rest of the world from using either military force or economic sanctions to topple the regime.”⁴⁾ Bennett and Lind, however, see a such collapse as far more likely and assess how such an event might be responded to in order to further US interests.⁵⁾ In contrast,

1) Henry Louis Mencken, *In Defense of Women*, Philip Goodman, 1918.

2) Carlo Davis, Jared Feldschreiber, and Sarah Lipkis, ‘Anatomy: World’s Most Isolated Countries’, *World Policy Journal*, Spring 2013.

3) Richard Fontaine and Micah Springut, ‘Managing North Korea: The Need for Coordination between Washington and Seoul’, *National Security Journal*, 13 May 2013.

4) Robert D. Kaplan and Abraham M. Denmark, ‘The Long Goodbye: The Future North Korea’, *World Affairs*, June 2011.

5) Bruce W. Bennett and Jennifer Lind, ‘The Collapse of North Korea: Military Missions and Requirements’, *International Security*, 2 (36), Fall 2011, 84-119.

Hughes considers the danger posed by the DPRK to have been overplayed for political purposes but, nonetheless, still views it as a serious threat to Japan and the key driver of both Japan's remilitarization and support for broader US military operations.⁶⁾ While it is important to address any legitimate security concerns the DPRK poses, any exaggeration or distortion of such threats risks skewing the prioritization of the aims of engagement with the DPRK, and of compromising the ability of other states to promote political reform within the DPRK itself. This paper argues that a refocusing is required, that would shift perception of the DPRK from being a military threat to its neighbours, to one in which economic support and encouragement for humanitarian reform offer a clearer path for peaceful integration of the DPRK into the regional community, as well as for promoting Japan's long-term security.

In order to make any significant breakthrough in relations with the solitary state, Japan will have to reassess the extent of the actual military threat posed and weigh the value of expensive and destabilizing military or economic responses against the potential benefits of engagement via proactive diplomatic initiatives. Such efforts are likely to be politically risky for any statesman concerned about being seen as 'soft' on the North, as both some domestic Japanese elements and Japan's regional allies favor more forceful, less conciliatory strategies. Yet, a failure to seize such opportunities while they remain may see Japan lose any real hope of gaining political capital from bilateral relations and instead relegate it to either enduring the uncertain and insecure status quo of an armed and hostile DPRK, or awaiting a collapse of the Kim regime, an event that will shift the regional balance of power in ways unlikely to favor Japan.

Both the dangers of potential regime collapse and the unreliable nature of the mass media were highlighted during the recent absence from public life of the DPRK's leader, Kim Jong-Un. For more than a month the head of state failed to appear in any way, including for a number of politically significant public events, fuelling speculation that he was seriously ill, had actually died, or had been removed in a coup.⁷⁾ It was known, however,

6) Christopher Hughes, 'Super-sizing the DPRK Threat: Japan's Evolving Military Posture and North Korea', *Asian Survey*, Vol. 49, No. 2, 2009, 299

7) Sangwon Yoon, 'What's Up With North Korea's Kim? It's a Mystery to CIA', *Bloomberg*, 9 October 2014; Paul French, 'Disappearance of North Korea's Kim Jong Un Could Ease Path to Peace, Coup or No', *Reuters*, 8 October 2014.

that he had injured his ankle and, given that ankle surgery routinely takes more than a month of bed rest to recover from, it was not especially unusual that a leader obsessed with promoting an image of strength might avoid public appearances. It was also not unprecedented, as both his father and grandfather entered similar periods of reclusiveness following medical treatment. When he did finally reappear the major impact was highlighting how little information on the internal politics of the DPRK is available to external observers and how ill-prepared the latter are to accurately assess the likely impact and long-term implications of sudden, dramatic change, whether stemming from a death, coup or some other factor. In Japan's case, relations with the DPRK have not been formalized since 1948. Normalization talks have repeatedly stalled due to an inability to resolve issues such as reparations for colonial rule, the abduction issue, the DPRK's failure to comply with IAEA regulations, and related weapon development programs. Ongoing ties are subject to sudden and dramatic fluctuation and minor acts can have much larger symbolic repercussions. Currently, Japan has the world's most negative view on the DPRK (more so than either South Korea or the USA) with 92% of the public holding unfavorable views of the state.⁸⁾ Hideshi Takesada, director of the National Institute of Defense Studies, calls the DPRK an imminent threat, as opposed to China's medium-term threat.⁹⁾ In response, the US has urged allies to enhance Ballistic Missile Defense (BMD) systems and take 'firm action' against the so-called rogue state.¹⁰⁾ The danger posed by the DPRK is, however, far from clear and considerable questions remain regarding whether a military response by Japan will alleviate or exacerbate the dilemma.

THE MILITARY THREAT

The US has frequently declared the DPRK to be a legitimate threat to continental America.¹¹⁾ If we weigh the world's sole military superpower (\$640 billion in defense spending/year) against a third-world country with limit-

8) *2013 Country Ratings Poll*, GlobeScan/PIPA, 22 May 2013.

9) 'China's Military a Global Concern: Japan', *India Today*, 17 December 2010.

10) Bruce Klinger, 'North Korean Missile Defiance Requires a Stern Response', *The Heritage Foundation*, 12 December 2012.

11) 'Gates: North Korea Will Pose Direct Threat to US', *AP*, 11 January 2011.

ed electricity supplies, widespread malnourishment and an entire GDP less than that of the city of Tulsa in the USA, it seems strange to think that such a colossal disparity can exist and a potential David and Goliath scenario still occur.¹²⁾ Nonetheless, in recent years American books, games and movies have portrayed the fantasy scenario of a North Korean invasion of the USA, an impossibility that, nonetheless, feeds into media fear-mongering regarding the DPRK 'threat'.¹³⁾ A recent bugbear was the danger of Electro-Magnetic Pulse (EMP) weapons that supposedly threaten America's entire electrical network, something the Director of the US Task Force on National and Homeland Security called "an EMP apocalypse".¹⁴⁾ Requiring both advanced nuclear and ballistic missile programs, as well as cutting-edge research on EMP weaponization, such reports are far from credible considering the North's impoverished technological capabilities.¹⁵⁾ In Japan such fear-mongering has also been common. Hughes highlighted the role this played in using the DPRK's weapon development as a justification for Japanese military expansion, including sending troops to support the US in Iraq and participating in costly BMD procurement. Yet, he still believed that Japan had "genuine grounds for viewing North Korea as an existential threat".¹⁶⁾ Analysis of the DPRK's actual capabilities suggests, however, that what threat exists might be less damaging to Japan than the expensive countermeasures being promoted. BMD in particular, the development of billion-dollar land and sea based missile interceptors, remains a matter of considerable economic and strategic concern. The interceptors are of unproven practical application while the danger posed by the DPRK missiles seems greatly exaggerated, something David Albright, President of the Institute for Science and International Security, considers "up there with the Iraqi nuclear assessment."¹⁷⁾ Analysis of their missile program found it extremely outdated, small-scale, inaccurate, insufficient-

12) Palash R. Ghosh, 'North Korea: Huge Military, but Small Threat', *International Business Times*, 21 December 2011.

13) Robert Farley, 'Neocons Salivating Over Their Next Great Exaggerated Threat: Electromagnetic Pulse Attack', *Alternet*, 22 October 2009.

14) Peter Vincent Pry, 'North Korea EMP Attack Could Destroy U.S. - now', *Washington Times*, 19 December 2012.

15) Markus Schiller, *Characterizing the North Korean Nuclear Threat* (Santa Monica: RAND, 2012), 65.

16) Hughes, Op cit.

17) Anne Penketh, 'US Exaggerating Nuclear Threat From North Korea', *The Independent*, 3 March 2008;

ly tested, and vulnerable to preemptive strikes. Most importantly, it was assessed as being used primarily as a symbolic gesture of defiance and diplomatic bluff designed to win concessions during negotiations.¹⁸⁾ Some Japanese analysts support this view that tests are purely a bargaining tool and suggest that claims about their capability are disseminated by American intelligence to foster a sense of threat in Japan.¹⁹⁾ Others have offered analytical evidence showing that the DPRK's sabre-rattling is aimed more at reducing internal dissent.²⁰⁾ This is something US intelligence officials have themselves supported by admitting that the North's missiles would only be used in defense and then, only if the DPRK was on the verge of a military defeat.²¹⁾ Of course, the DPRK has been stating for years that its weapons are purely defensive in nature.²²⁾ Yet, none of this prevents a constant stream of media headlines such as recent claims that 'North Korea prepares rockets for US Strike', articles that fail to highlight the important point that the DPRK invariably issues its threats with the prefix "If the US or her allies attack us..."²³⁾

The ongoing development of nuclear weapons by the DPRK is something that draws an even stronger response, with tests in 2013 deemed a "grave threat" and "intolerable" by Japan's Prime Minister Abe.²⁴⁾ A sentiment echoed by China's President Xi,²⁵⁾ with the latter banning potential weapons exports to the DPRK in response.²⁶⁾ Yet some feel that the response to the tests is less about the dangers posed by the weapons themselves, which are less powerful than the first US Atomic-bombs, and whose use would mean national suicide for the DPRK, and more about a failure to

18) Schiller, Op cit. 73-74.

19) Hiroyuki Koshiji, 'Analysis: North Korean Threat to Japan', *UPI*, 19 March 2009

20) Robert Daniel Wallace, 'North Korea and Diversion: A quantitative Analysis', *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*, Vol. 47, No. 2, June 2014.

21) Denny Roy, 'Parsing Pyongyang's Strategy', *Survival*, Vol. 52, No. 2, February 2010. 111-136

22) 'Japan Preparing for External Expansion with US Support', *Korean Central News Agency*, 19 January 2012

23) 'North Korea's Kim Jong-Un 'Prepares Rockets for US Strike'', *Huffington Post*, 29 March 2013.

24) David Chance and Jack Kim, 'North Korea Nuclear Test Draws Anger, Including from China', *Reuters*, 12 February 2013.

25) 'Containing the North Korean Threat', *Bloomberg*, 4 February 2013.

26) Jane Perlez, 'China Bans Items for Export to North Korea, Fearing Their Use in Weapons', *New York Times*, 24 September 2013.

understand or accommodate the needs of the DPRK government.²⁷⁾

In 2003 the US told the DPRK it should learn a lesson from Iraq's invasion.²⁸⁾ While undoubtedly meant as a threat, it would seem that the message the DPRK received was that Iraq's lack of Weapons of Mass Destruction (WMDs) was what led to the country's invasion. This is a perfectly rational analysis on their part and Western states themselves justify their possession of nuclear weapons by saying they "prevent acts of aggression against vital interests that cannot be countered by other means".²⁹⁾ Such views can only have been enhanced by the speed with which Western states turned upon Libya's Gaddafi, who only a few years before his overthrow and death was viewed in the West as a reformed ally. The ongoing efforts to promote regime change in Syria mere months after the Assad government willingly destroyed its own chemical weapon stockpiles no doubt reinforce this message. Despite this the US is still capable of claiming with a straight face that, regarding its foreign policy, "in line with American public preferences...the Obama administration has shown hesitancy to pursue unilateral military interventions."³⁰⁾ Yet, North Korea has quite legitimate and inarguable grounds for concern; the US, despite its protestations, is a regular proponent of regime change by both direct and indirect means, continues to engage in unilateral drone bombing campaigns in numerous countries, has political and economic values which completely clash with those of the DPRK and, along with its allies Japan and South Korea, spends roughly seventy times more on military development than the DPRK.

If it can be accepted that the DPRK is driven militarily by defensive aims and that it realizes aggressive action against other states would be suicidal, why should Japan and China regard their possession of a nuclear safeguard as "intolerable"? Clearly nuclear proliferation is undesirable, yet in the case of the DPRK the genie is out of the bottle. It is all too easy to say the North 'should not have' such weapons and many valid reasons exist to support such a view. The reality, however, is that they 'have' the weapons

27) Wade L. Huntley, 'US Policy Toward North Korea in Strategic Context', *Asian Survey*, Vol. 47, No. 3, June 2007, 455-480.

28) 'US tells Iran, Syria, N. Korea 'Learn from Iraq'', *Reuters*, 9 April 2003.

29) Michael Fallon, *Maintaining an Effective, Independent Nuclear Deterrent*, UK Ministry of Defense, 12 December 2012.

30) Scott Snyder, 'US Policy toward North Korea', *SERI Quarterly*, January 2013, 101.

and it is now a question of whether accepting their possession might actually promote peace and stability, or, whether attempting to force them to relinquish their weapons might generate a military crisis, civil war, regime collapse, humanitarian disaster, or alternate WMD event. Alongside the DPRK, India, Pakistan and Israel also possesses nuclear weapons despite not being recognized as nuclear powers by the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty (NPT). In Israel the official policy is one of 'nuclear ambiguity', something the US accepted following Israeli guarantees that they would not be the first to use such weapons in the Middle East. For the DPRK, acceptance of the existence of such weapons, by its neighbors, could reduce the state's fear and tension regarding foreign aggression enough to permit the ten or twenty years of political, economic and humanitarian reform it would require to make the possession of the devices no longer necessary. Clearly the adoption of a policy of toleration would be unlikely to please a public that likes simple answers and which has been conditioned by decades of media stories to have an ingrained fear-response to anything North Korean. Yet, in rational terms, why should it be less reasonable to ask the DPRK's neighbors to live with a potential threat the DPRK has itself endured for decades? Even during the Korean War, the US was considering using nuclear weapons against the North,³¹⁾ with deployment of US nuclear weapons to South Korea beginning in 1958 and continuing until 1991, during which time South Korea also began its own, short-lived, nuclear weapons program.³²⁾ The removal of weapons from South Korea merely represented a shift to off-shore targeting which began in 1993,³³⁾ while 2002 saw the US Nuclear Posture Review call for the creation of contingency plans for nuclear strike capabilities against the DPRK.³⁴⁾ The US has since then, consistently reminded the DPRK that it faces the threat of US nuclear attack, with Colin Powell, acting as Chairman of the Joint Chiefs of Staff, going so far as to state that the US was capable of turning the North into "a charcoal briquette".³⁵⁾ Needless to say, neither

31) Charles J. Hanley and Randy Hershafft, "U.S. Often Weighed N. Korea Nuke Option", *AP*, October 11, 2010.

32) Daniel A. Pinkston, 'South Korea's Nuclear Experiments,' *CNS Research Story*, 9 November 2004.

33) Bruce Cumings, *Korea's Place in the Sun: A Modern History*, (W.W. Norton & Company, 2005), 488-489.

34) US Nuclear Posture Review 2002 (Excerpts), December 31, 2001, www.globalsecurity.org.

35) Bruce Cumings, 'Latest North Korean Provocations Stem from Missed US Opportunities

nuclear proliferation nor living with the threat of nuclear attack are good things. Yet, there is no reasonable grounds wherein it is legitimate to target the DPRK with nuclear weapons and also declare it "intolerable" that they possess the same deterrent threat. The NPT was framed as an agreement that non-nuclear states would refrain from seeking weapons technology, while nuclear states would work to share the benefits of peaceful nuclear technology and dismantle their nuclear stockpiles. In its negotiations with the DPRK the US has repeatedly tried to curtail the former's non-military nuclear research programs,³⁶⁾ while the US itself has recently embarked on a 30 year, \$1 trillion program to enhance its nuclear weapons capabilities.³⁷⁾ As such, neither the DPRK nor the US are abiding by the NPT's principles, although only the latter are claiming to do so (the DPRK having withdrawn from the NPT in 2003).

Returning to the questioning of 'Should the DPRK have nuclear weapons?', clearly, in an ideal world, their possession would not be necessary and would, in fact, be counter to the state's security interests. In contrast, the question of 'Why does the DPRK has nuclear weapons?', can be directly attributed to the sense of threat projected by the US. In asking 'How did they come to have them?', at least part of the blame for the failure of six-party talks has to be laid upon participants other than the DPRK alone. The remaining question then is 'What factors make tolerance of DPRK's nuclear status less acceptable than that of India, Pakistan and Israel?' The suggestion that the DPRK represents an unpredictable and plausible threat to its neighbours would, if true, remain so regardless of whether it curtailed future nuclear and missile research. The DPRK currently has more than enough WMDs to pose a genuine security threat should it be determined to create one. It possesses 2500-5000 tons of biological weapons, similar supplies of chemical weapons,³⁸⁾ and a stockpile of 6-12 nuclear devices.³⁹⁾ Despite fears of missile tests, if the DPRK wanted to use such

for Demilitarization,' *Democracy Now*, May 29, 2009.

36) Han Lheem 'China's New Approach to North Korean Nuclear Issue', in Sujian Guo, Shipping Hua (eds), *New Dimensions of Chinese Foreign Policy* (New York: Lexington Books, 2009), 156.

37) William J. Broad and David E. Sangersept, 'U.S. Ramping Up Major Renewal in Nuclear Arms', *New York Times*, 21 September 2014.

38) 'Arms Control and Proliferation Profile: North Korea', *Arms Control Association*. April 2013.

39) 'North Korea Defense and Security Report 2014', *Business Monitor International*, October 2014, 27-28.

weapons against Japan it could easily smuggle one onto a ship bound for a Japanese port. A US study determined that a relatively small nuclear weapon detonated at a major port could kill 60,000 people, expose 150,000 more to radiation, and do ten times more financial damage than 9/11.⁴⁰⁾ By applying this to Japan and imagining a scenario targeting Japan's Keihin (Yokohama-hub), Hanshin (Osaka-hub) and Nagoya ports, such an attack would shut down more than 500 million cubic meters of daily shipping, necessitate the evacuation of millions of people from the affected areas, and cripple Japan's economy. Yet for some reason the DPRK's faulty, outdated missiles are presented as a more serious threat when, in fact, they primarily serve to justify military growth that is directed far more at China, with the BMD system in particular negating China's own defensive deterrent capability and promoting military escalation.⁴¹⁾ China itself fears that acceptance of DPRK nuclear weapons could lead to regional proliferation by Japan or South Korea, yet these are merely possibilities when weighed against the certainty that BMD proliferation based upon the insubstantial DPRK threat is a detrimentally exacerbating factor in the regional security dilemma. In addition to this is the likelihood that no level of disarmament on the part of the DPRK would ever be sufficient for its critics and that, as in the case of Iraqi WMDs, it would be impossible to prove negative possession.

The DPRK remains committed to its nuclear policy, but in such a way that it may actually reduce the militarization of the state. Since its inception the DPRK has followed a 'military first' (Songun) policy in which all state resources are directed, first and foremost, to the promotion of the military. It is a system which has allowed an impoverished state to maintain a military force far beyond its practical means, but which has also led to a tiered social class in which military personnel are preeminent, promoted widespread corruption, and diverted investment away from economic reform. Under Kim Jong-Un, the country is instead adopting a dual program focusing on nuclear defense and light industry with the assumption that the nuclear deterrent will allow reductions in military spending that can be better invested in developing the economy. Recent analysis has at times

40) Charles Meade and Roger Molander, 'Considering the Effects of a Catastrophic Terrorist Attack', *RAND*, 2006.

41) Gavan Patrick Gray, 'Japanese Defense Production, National Security and Alliance Relations in the 21st Century', *PhD Dissertation*, Leicester University, October 2014, 182-200.

highlighted surges in DPRK defense spending, yet these have been during periods of major inflation, meaning that military spending (in dollar terms) has been constrained.⁴²⁾ There has also been an apparent cull of influential military figures, such as General Ri Yong-ho, who voiced opposition to the reforms.⁴³⁾ Elsewhere, privileges of army commanders have been rolled back, and scholars sent abroad to study Chinese economic models of limited capitalism. While small, these changes are highly significant and suggest that diplomatic negotiation supporting such reforms could have considerable impact upon North Korea's future development.⁴⁴⁾ Of course, the country remains highly repressive and negotiations must consider humanitarian requirements, yet, there is little evidence that Japan will be required to field a military, rather than diplomatic or economic, response to the DPRK.

REGIME COLLAPSE

A further threat that stands of more legitimate concern than a missile or nuclear attack is the danger of sudden collapse itself. A variety of factors including, civil unrest, a military coup, political infighting or natural disaster, could lead to a breakdown in governance that would signal the end of the current DPRK leadership and possibly lead to a humanitarian disaster involving civil war, massive refugee migration, starvation and the proliferation of WMDs. The lion's share of responsibility for dealing with this crisis would fall upon South Korea and estimated costs now stand at \$2-3 trillion.⁴⁵⁾ At very best it would require an allocation of 10% or more of the national budget for at least a decade. A worst case scenario would additionally see massive amounts of troops needed for humanitarian assistance, border control, internal security, civil disarmament and the safeguarding of WMDs,⁴⁶⁾ with some estimates requiring a minimum of 400,000.⁴⁷⁾ This would most likely be a combination of South Korean and

42) 'North Korea Defense and Security Report 2014', *Business Monitor International*, 14.

43) Justin McCurry, 'North Korean Leader Kim Jong-un Wrests Economic Control from Military', *The Guardian*, 20 July 2012.

44) Blaine Harden, 'North Korea's Extreme Makeover', *Foreign Policy*, 26 July 2012.

45) Andrew Bennett and Cory S. Julie, 'The US, China and Preparing for North Korea's Demise', *CSIS*, 31 January 2011.

46) Mark Fitzpatrick, 'North Korean Security Challenges: A net Assessment', *ISIS*, 2011

47) Bruce W. Bennett and Jennifer Lind, 'The Collapse of North Korea: Military, Missions and

US forces, with some US commentators viewing Japanese participation as both “unlikely and undesirable”, suggesting that it be restricted to offering increased basing for US personnel.⁴⁸⁾ Potential collapse is something the former countries have been preparing for for more than a decade (under the name OPLAN 5029) but the prospect itself has been viewed increasingly negatively by South Korean citizens who are wary of the potentially massive bill involved and the impact integration would have on their own quality of life. Both the Lee and Park governments have made efforts to boost public support for reunification, though with little result so far. This might change, however, if development of DPRK mineral resources worth an estimated \$6 trillion begins to show returns. These deposits of highly valuable Rare Earth Minerals (REMs), discovered in 2011, have the potential to radically alter the economic fortunes of both the DPRK and any country that gains significant mining rights from it. The South now sees this mineral wealth, alongside the economic boost from millions of new workers, as a solution to concerns over the financial cost of reunification, currently the key factor generating opposition to the scenario among the South Korean public.⁴⁹⁾

A unified Korea would, however, be unlikely to promote Japanese security. Among international states the two Koreas share the most negative views of Japan and both have a long-history of using anti-Japanese propaganda to promote domestic national unity. Efforts to overcome the strains caused by the economic, political and cultural differences between a reunified North and South would be likely to play heavily upon this shared history of common enmity. Any belief that the security situation would become more stable is also an illusion. The US military presence in Asia would not diminish, instead it would push itself further north to the edge of the Chinese border (with China similarly scrambling to create some form of buffer zone in the remains of the DPRK). The potential for clashes between North and South Korea would simply be replaced by potential clashes between Chinese and US/Korean troops. Also, with a larger, more stable, peninsular base and no need to commit troops to balancing the North, the US might feel less dependent upon Japan for support, raising the risk of abandonment that so worries Japanese leadership. The latter group would

Requirements’, *International Security*, Vol. 36, No. 2, Fall 2011, 84-119.

48) Ibid.

49) ‘4 Out of 10 S. Koreans Unwilling to Shoulder Unification Cost: Poll’, *Yonhap*, 7 May 2014.

also find themselves deprived of their favored justification for military expansion, with any further growth guaranteed to increase tensions with China. A collapse would thus bring both dangers and potential gains, yet without a clear strategy in place for how to utilize the situation, as seems to be the case with Japan, any positive results for the latter state are unlikely and the collapse/reunification scenario should be seen as unfavorable outcome. The clear alternative is to engage with the DPRK in a way that will support their economic development and use the carrot of security, stability and increased quality of life as a means of promoting diplomatic engagement, human rights reform and greater transparency.

ECONOMIC REFORM

With an estimated GDP of only \$40 billion the DPRK is economically fragile and Japan, as its third largest trading partner, is in a position to promote dramatic stabilization through focused economic support. This is particularly important following the DPRK's 2009 redenomination of the won, a move which generated a rare wave of popular discontent with government policy and which signalled the potential for increased unrest should current efforts at reform fail in their intended aims.⁵⁰⁾

The DPRK has no private companies, all trade is centrally administered and goods are provided via a distribution system rather than markets. Recently, however, Pak Pong-Ju has been reinstated as Premier of the DPRK, having served a previous term from 2003-2007. His political excommunication at that time was seen as punishment for having pushed too strongly for a market-oriented economic model, just as his resurrection is seen as a potential acknowledgement of the failure of the central rationing system.⁵¹⁾ Pak has introduced countermeasures which allow a form of quasi-private ownership in which farmers and factories are allowed retain surpluses which can then be sold on the increasingly tolerated black markets.⁵²⁾ The programs seem to have already lead to considerable growth in both the agricultural and industrial sectors, with the shift to-

50) Tania Branigan, 'North Korean Finance Chief Executed for Botched Currency Reform', *The Guardian*, 18 March 2010.

51) Choe Sang-hun, 'North Korea Reinstates Market-Oriented Official', *New York Times*, 23 August 2010.

52) Yong Sueng Dong, 'Sign of Economic Change in North Korea', *SERI Quarterly*, July 2013.

ward light industry helping to reduce the state's electricity demands. Trade with China in particular, has grown dramatically, with imports doubling between 2010 and 2013 and exports showing slow but steady growth.⁵³⁾ This has seen the DPRK reduce its dependency on the South, only to replace it with a growing reliance upon China. The execution of Kim Jong-Un's uncle, Jang Sung-Taek, shocked many in China, where he had been the DPRK's point man, yet others considered his fall as resulting, in part, from his having become too close to China.⁵⁴⁾ Cross-border trade has given rise to a growing number of potential oligarchs who will seek to amass personal fortunes from any liberalization, as was the case in 2003 when a major project to establish a Special Administrative Region in Sinuiju, modeled on Hong Kong and Macao, was set aside after its governor was arrested for embezzlement. The DPRK hopes to reduce its economic dependency upon China, and thus China's influence over internal political affairs, by extending a wider net of regional collaboration.

In recent years it has made efforts to build ties with small and medium-sized countries such as Mongolia, Canada and Australia, something the lucrative mining-rights and potential capital returns from its REM deposits should make increasingly easy.⁵⁵⁾ These deposits will, if properly developed, also offer leverage in negotiations with Japan, South Korea and China, currently the three top importers of REMs.⁵⁶⁾ Another significant partner exists in Russia, who is hoping to extend a rail connection through the DPRK to the South, something which would allow for a new Eurasian transport corridor running from South Korea's ports to the center of Europe. Already a Russian rail link has been opened with the Rajin-Sonbong Special Economic Zone and Russia's recent decision to write off \$11 billion in DPRK debt was seen as a commitment to future joint infrastructure projects including a possible gas line from Russia's Sakhalin fields.⁵⁷⁾ The mayor of the Japanese town of Sakaiminato visited the Rajin area in 2014

53) Henri Feron, 'Doom and Gloom or Economic Boom? The Myth of the North Korean Economic Collapse', *The Asia Pacific Journal*, Vol. 12, 5 May 2014.

54) Alexandre Mansourov, 'North Korea: The Dramatic Fall of Jang Song Thaek', *SAIS*, 9 December 2013.

55) Migeddorj Batchimeg, 'Mongolia's DPRK Policy: Engaging North Korea', *Asian Survey*, Vol. 46, No. 2, March 2006, 275-297.

56) Marc Humphries, 'Rare Earth Metals: The Global Supply Chain', CSR Report for Congress, 16 December 2013.

57) Zachary Keck, 'Eyeing Pipeline, Russia Forgives North Korean Debt', *The Diplomat*, 22 April 2014.

to assess its potential for bilateral trade ventures, which inarguably exist, yet it was not an officially sanctioned government visit.⁵⁸⁾ Japan cannot afford to delay though, as not only Russia, but also China and South Korea will be eager to take advantage of any development projects that might extend their influence in the DPRK. Japan's advantage lies in the fact that, for China and South Korea at least, the DPRK wishes to avoid becoming over-dependent and Japan should therefore have a strong opportunity to make inroads. The Kaesong Industrial Complex has been a highly successful venture between the North and South, something Japan could potentially replicate with Rajin and use as a jumping-off point for further joint initiatives. However, one sticking point between Japan and the DPRK has been the issue of reparations for the colonial period and one possible way to answer this would be through economic investment. The areas of mining, transportation and energy supply are clearly of vital importance but Japan can also raise the DPRK's dependency upon Japan, and thus the influence Japan wields, by assisting the growth of its light manufacturing industry as well as other areas of direct benefit to the populace such a medical services and education. A failure to at least attempt to make such initiatives will see influence over the DPRK policy-making fall upon other states, and Japan's opportunity to improve its beleaguered ties with the people of the DPRK slip away. Any such attempts would, however, be dependent upon Japan ending, or at least further curtailing, its sanctions against the DPRK.

SANCTIONS

When asked to define US policy toward the DPRK John Bolton, as US Secretary for Arms Control, responded by displaying the cover of the book 'The End of North Korea'.⁵⁹⁾ International isolation and particularly the economic constraints of sanctions have certainly played their part in weakening the country, with Bolton's then boss, George W. Bush, declaring the DPRK the most sanctioned nation in the world.⁶⁰⁾ Despite this, there

58) 'Japan Mayor Says N. Korea Trip Aimed to See Seaport's Trade Potential', *Japan Economic Newswire*, 22 August 2014.

59) 'Absent from the Korea Talks: Bush's Hard-liner', *New York Times*, 2 September 2003.

60) 'Remarks by President Bush and Prime Minister Fukuda of Japan in Joint Press Availability', *Business Wire*, 6 July 2008

are some who feel that not enough has been done in this regard, such as Kurt Campbell, formerly with the US State Department and now CEO of the Asia Group, who recently advocated tougher sanctions, suggesting that there is room to increase them tenfold.⁶¹⁾

The key problem of sanctions is that rather than resolving any problem they intensify it, essentially engaging in a 'game of chicken' to see who will be the first to capitulate. In a country as politically and economically precarious as the DPRK this simply promotes higher levels of instability, and any potential weaknesses, be they food shortages, economic failure or an attack on the luxuries enjoyed by the political elite, are most likely to produce only higher levels of brinksmanship.⁶²⁾ Other attempts at instilling compliance through withholding aid supplies have also been found to be counterproductive, with other states stepping in to fill the gap, negating meaningful impact and making the provision of aid useful only as a reward for good behavior rather than a punishment.⁶³⁾ The DPRK's resilience against sanctions is only likely to increase as growth in agriculture and light industry allow it to better endure shortfalls from external sources. Rather than pursuing a failing tactic Japan is capable of utilizing the reduction of sanctions as a bargaining chip in its negotiations, something already displayed by a significant easing during the Summer of 2014 which saw the lifting of a ban on DPRK nationals from entering Japan, easing of restrictions of Chongryon officials (the de facto DPRK political representatives in Japan) travelling between the two countries, permission for DPRK vessels to enter Japanese ports for humanitarian purposes, and some other minor concessions. While a positive step, many barriers still remain in place, including, the banning of DPRK vessels (including the symbolically important Mongyongbong, a passenger ferry which acts as the only direct travel connection between the DPRK and Japan) from entering Japanese ports for commercial purposes and a ban on chartered flights between the two states. Other sticking points are ongoing asset freezes on parties involved in WMD programs, a lack of any DPRK embas-

61) 'U.S. Needs to Toughen Sanctions on Recalcitrant N. Korea: Campbell', *Yonhap*, 2 October 2014.

62) Yong Kwon, 'Food Before Politics on North Korea', *Asia Times*, 6 October 2011; and, Hughes, *Op cit.* 298.

63) Marie Soderberg, 'Can Japanese Foreign Aid to North Korea Create Peace and Stability', *Pacific Affairs*, Vol. 79, No. 3, Fall 2006, 450.

sy in Japan, and most importantly a full ban on imports and exports that is due to last until April 2015.⁶⁴⁾ As a result, there exists significant room for Japan to offer concessions in building a better relationship with the DPRK, some of which would be relatively minor (such as allowing the Japanese women who emigrated to the DPRK with Korean husbands to visit Japan) and others which would be far more significant (such as establishing direct flights between Japan and the DPRK). For many though the relaxation of Japanese sanctions or other barriers is dependent upon the DPRK first addressing its history of human rights abuse especially, for Japan, the question of abductions.

HUMAN RIGHTS

The United Nations Human Rights Commission has declared that the violations carried out by the DPRK are of “a gravity, scale and nature...that does not have any parallel in the contemporary world”,⁶⁵⁾ and for many such a pronouncement is the final word on the issue. The group's report chastises the international community for not having done enough in response and states that the violations “meet the high threshold required for proof of crimes against humanity in international law”.⁶⁶⁾ Taken together, such pronouncements are extremely dangerous for the DPRK in an era in which Western states are quite capable of using this alone as justification for a bombing campaign driven by the ‘Responsibility to Protect’. In fact, it is not unreasonable to think that such a campaign might have already begun, as recently occurred in Libya, if the DPRK had not possessed a nuclear deterrent.

While the group's report does provide substantial testimonial evidence of severe and widespread abuse that should certainly be acted upon by the international community, there are some caveats that should be applied. Firstly, the report relies primarily upon witness testimony to generate “reasonable grounds” for belief. The United Nation's fact-finding missions and truth commissions generally use four standards of proof, of which ‘rea-

64) ‘Extension of Ban on Imports from and Exports to North Korea, Pursuant to the Foreign Exchange and Foreign Trade Act’, *METI Japan*, 14 April 2013.

65) *Report of the Commission of Inquiry on Human Rights in the DPRK*, UN Human Rights Council, 7 February 2014, 18.

66) *Ibid.* p. 16.

sonable grounds' is the weakest.⁶⁷⁾ This in no way alters the severity of the allegations or the need to address them but it does suggest that more information needs to be gathered before a concrete verdict regarding their severity and extent can be applied. One reason for exhibiting caution in this regard lies with the fact that the majority of testimony has come from defectors who, according to Donald MacIntyre, former Seoul Bureau Chief for Time Magazine, frequently receive substantial payments for stories which they are encouraged to dramatize.⁶⁸⁾ While enough of these stories independently corroborate one-another to justify 'reasonable grounds', they cannot simply be taken as unadorned truth. In the biography of Shin Dong-Hyuk, a former prisoner in a DPRK labour camp, he admits altering his account of events and the author acknowledges that,

"Accounts of what goes on inside (labour camps) cannot be independently verified. Although satellite images have greatly added to outside understanding of the camps, defectors remain the primary sources of information and their motives and credibility are not spotless. In South Korea and elsewhere, they are often desperate to make a living, willing to confirm the preconceptions of human rights activists, anti-communist missionaries, and right-wing ideologues. Some camp survivors refuse to talk unless they are paid cash upfront. Others repeated juicy anecdotes they had heard but not personally witnessed."⁶⁹⁾

Uncritical acceptance of even outrageous claims regarding the DPRK has, however, become common for media outlets. The, now debunked, examples of Kim Jong-Un having a former girlfriend executed or throwing his uncle to a pack of starving dogs are only the most egregious of a long-standing pattern of sensationalism and distortion.⁷⁰⁾ Some of the claims of the UN report have also been challenged by China, whose official response stated that many of the supposed 'political refugees' it repatriated to the DPRK were in fact economic migrants, smugglers and poachers who, following re-

67) Stephen Wilkinson, 'Standards of Proof in International Humanitarian and Human Rights Fact-Finding and Inquiry Missions', *Geneva Academy of International Humanitarian Law*, 29 April 2011. p. 5.

68) Donald MacIntyre, 'U.S. Media and the Korean peninsula', in Donald Kirk and Choe Sang Hun (eds), *Korea Witness: 135 Years of War, Crisis, and News in the Land of the Morning Calm*, (EunHaeng NaMu Publishing, 2006), 406.

69) Blaine Harden, *Escape from Camp 14* (New York: Penguin, 2013), 12.

70) 'Kim Jong-Un's Ex-Girlfriend 'Shot by Firing Squad'', Chosun Ilbo, 29 August 2013; 'Kim Jong Un's Executed Uncle Was Eaten Alive by 120 Hungry Dogs: Report', *NBC News*, 3 January 2014.

turn to the DPRK, repeatedly reentered China, suggesting that they were not being either executed or dispatched to prison camps as the report had claimed.⁷¹⁾

US Senator Sam Brownback, argued in 2008 that the DPRK leadership should be given “a stark choice: transparency or extinction”,⁷²⁾ and the former is certainly a reasonable demand. It cannot, however, be accompanied in the same breath with extreme threats and hope to have any chance of success. It is instead important to recognize the likely fears of the DPRK leadership that, should increased transparency reveal any form of abuse, this will be used by the West to generate increased support for regime change. The DPRK has repeatedly charged that the human rights issue is being used by the West as a tool of regime change and that resolutions criticizing its rights record have been introduced whenever the DPRK failed to comply with Western demands in other areas.⁷³⁾ Unfortunately the DPRK is, at times, its own worst enemy, with their response to the most recent UN report also attacking Japan for rampant child slavery and personally condemning one of the authors of the UN report for being homosexual.⁷⁴⁾ Nonetheless, the underlying question, of whether the campaign for greater human rights is directed at regime change or actually improving living conditions of those involved, is an important one.

There has long been a clear split regarding the promotion of DPRK human rights between two camps: those focusing on civil and political rights (CPR) and those focusing on economic, social and cultural rights (ESCR). The CPR advocates have typically advanced the necessity of regime change based upon the issue of human rights abuse, while ESCR has instead focused upon the need to improve the living standards of the people of the DPRK separate from issues of political change. CPR groups typically adhere to US policy on the DPRK, something that is frequently opposed by ESCR groups who see the inevitable destabilization that would result from regime change as being inimicable to the welfare of the people of the

71) *Report of the Commission of Inquiry on Human Rights in the Democratic People's Republic of Korea*, 33-34.

72) Cited in Christine Hong, 'War by Other Means: The Violence of North Korean Human Rights', *The Asia-Pacific Journal*, Vol. 12, Issue 13, No. 2, March 31, 2014.

73) 'Report of the DPRK Association for Human Rights Studies', *Korean Central News Agency*, 13 September 2014.

74) 'KCNA Commentary Slams Artifice by Political Swindlers', *Korean Central News Agency*, 22 April 2014.

North (an example being the differing responses of both groups to the 2004 US North Korean Human Rights Act).⁷⁵⁾ When speaking of ‘human rights’ it is, therefore, very important to understand the actual aims and likelihood of success of policy proposals.

The DPRK also claim that they are being singled out, with other states that possess equally questionable records on human rights, being either ignored or made active allies of the West. It would certainly help to negate such claims of hypocrisy if critics of the DPRK were as active in challenging the abuses of countries such as Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, Uzbekistan, Cambodia, Rwanda or Ethiopia.⁷⁶⁾ In the US the ‘Leahy Law’ is intended to prevent the US offering military support to any states guilty of human rights abuse, yet, in practice it is badly broken.⁷⁷⁾ In 2014 Somalia came bottom of a ranking of state corruption,⁷⁸⁾ and the US’s own analysis of the country stated:

“Civilian authorities did not maintain effective control over the security forces. Security forces committed human rights abuses....impunity remained the norm. Governmental authorities took minimal steps to prosecute and punish officials who committed abuses, particularly military and police officials accused of committing rape, killings, and extortion of civilians.”⁷⁹⁾

Despite this, in the same year, the White House approved the supply of military aid to Somalia.⁸⁰⁾ Similar conditions exist in Chad, where the US found security forces to be involved in extra-judicial killings and torture,⁸¹⁾ yet still proceeded with plans for training Chad’s military personnel.⁸²⁾

75) Moon Kyungyon, ‘South Korean Civil Society Organizations, Human Rights Norms and North Korea’, *Critical Asian Studies*, Vol. 46, No. 1, 2014, 80.

76) Kenneth Roth, ‘Barack Obama: Dump These 8 Unsavory Allies’, *Human Rights Watch*, 2 January 2013.

77) Schmitt, Eric, ‘Military Says Law Barring U.S. Aid to Rights Violators Hurts Training Mission’, *The New York Times*, 20 June 2013; Winifred Tate, ‘Human Rights Law and Military Aid Delivery: A Case Study of the Leahy Law’, *Political and Legal Anthropology Review*, 34 (2), November 2011, 337–354.

78) Corruption Perception Index 2014, Transparency International, <http://www.transparency.org/cpi2014/results>

79) Somalia 2013 Human Rights Report, United States Department of State, Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights and Labor, 2013, 1-2.

80) ‘Obama approves sending U.S. military aid to Somalia’, *Reuters*, 8 April 2013.

81) Chad 2013 Human Rights Report, United States Department of State, Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights and Labor, 2013, 1.

82) Mindy Anderson, ‘USARAF Trains 4,000 Troops in Chad, Guinea, Malawi’, U.S. Army Afri-

These double standards undermine efforts to place pressure upon the DPRK by suggesting that any legitimate concern in the West over rights abuse, takes second place to strategic concerns.

Calls for transparency need to be made alongside guarantees that the DPRK will be treated fairly, not threats to make it "extinct". The DPRK is equally unlikely to succumb to any internal grassroots pressure for reform; it lacks the technology that mobilized recent democratic movements,⁸³⁾ has no established internal opposition groups or minorities, and has no reason to believe violent repression would lower its international standing any further. States with a sincere interest in improving the humanitarian situation in the DPRK should realize that carrots, rather than sticks, must be employed. Economic and political stability, rather than threat and sanction-driven instability, is the only reliable basis upon which further reform can be pursued. With its recent relaxation of sanctions the Japanese government seems to recognize the greater value to be found in this softer path, yet a significant barrier remains to be crossed regarding the resolution of the longstanding 'abduction' issue.

ABDUCTIONS

Between 1977 and 1983 a number of Japanese citizens were kidnapped from Japan and taken to the DPRK for espionage purposes. The DPRK admits to 13 cases, the Japanese government recognizes 17, and there may be many others for which the evidence is less robust. Ever since, the issue has been a major barrier to normalizing diplomatic relations between the two states and it has become a key political target of the current Abe government. The UN report on Human Rights, considers the abductions a crime against humanity. There is no question that these events were heinous crimes, or that restitution should be made, but the manner in which the issue is handled, or mishandled, could have significant repercussions for bilateral relations and thus Japan's regional security. The Japanese government itself has explicitly stated that it will be impossible to normalize relations without resolving this issue.⁸⁴⁾ It is important therefore that

ca Public Affairs, 2 June 2014.

83) Yonho Kim, 'Cellphones in North Korea', *US-North Korea Institute, SAIS*, 2014, 29-30.

84) *Abductions of Japanese Citizens by North Korea*, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan, 2014, 12.

politicization of future negotiations does not occur, yet, given the strong emotions attached to the issue and the personal investment made by various politicians, including the current Prime Minister of Japan, hopes for true neutrality are small.

One question that could be asked is, if Japan has any interest in the ethical or legal aspect of the issue, why have successive Japanese governments never taken issue with the US policy of rendition? The US has, via the CIA, been involved in the kidnapping of dozens of individuals, the establishment of secret 'black' prisons, and the transfer of suspects to foreign states to enable their torture.⁸⁵⁾ The policy is directly comparable to the German 'Nacht und Nebel' disappearances during the Second World War, which the Nuremberg trials found to be crimes against humanity and war crimes under international law.⁸⁶⁾ As with condemnation of other human rights abuse in the DPRK, the criticisms lose force when they are not applied as a universal standard of judgement and will only serve to bolster the DPRK's use of the defence, reasonable or otherwise, that they are being unfairly singled out.

The Japanese government must also realize that there will never be a perfect resolution, something that should be clear from the difficulties involved in settling Japan's own historical legacy. There will always be some element of hardliners in both Japan and the DPRK who will view any compromise as capitulation. The Japanese government's position is that they require an investigation of roughly thirty cases known or strongly believed to have been abductions,⁸⁷⁾ yet an independent citizen's group investigating cases of possible abduction by the DPRK has compiled a list of 266 additional cases running from 1948 to 2003. It considers 77 of these as having a "high probability" while in the others a connection "cannot be ruled out".⁸⁸⁾ The latter standard is obviously something impossible for the DPRK government to ever fully satisfy and any sincere negotiation must offer the possibility of reaching a definitive political, if not criminal or civ-

85) Dick Marty, 'Alleged Secret Detentions and Unlawful Inter-State Transfers Involving Council of Europe Member States', *Council of Europe*, 7 June 2006, and Dick Marty, 'Abuse of State Secrecy and National Security', *Council of Europe*, 7 September 2011.

86) *Indictment, in The Trial of German Major War Criminals*, Proceedings of the International Military Tribunal Sitting at Nuremberg, Germany, 1946.

87) Headquarters for the Abduction Issue, Government of Japan. www.rachi.go.jp

88) Investigation Committee on Missing Japanese Probably Related to North Korea, (COM-JAN) <http://www.chosa-kai.jp/indexeng.htm>

il, resolution. The DPRK has said that it is still investigating the original 17 victims but only plans to provide further information on the other cases which the Japanese government suspects but which have not been acknowledged officially.⁸⁹⁾ Additionally, it is investigating the status of some 1,400 Japanese women married to DPRK men, and the remains of up to 20,000 Japanese soldiers believed to be buried in the DPRK.⁹⁰⁾ Japan has, however, rejected this approach, requiring that new information also be provided on the original victims, with some commentators declaring that "North Korea must be aware of the whereabouts of victims of abduction."⁹¹⁾ Unfortunately, this is not necessarily the case. If the abduction program was carried out on the personal orders of Kim Il Sung, detailed knowledge of it might be limited to a small handful of people and whether they are still alive 20-30 years later is far from certain, particularly given the alleged purges which have taken place in the interim. The Russian author Mikhail Bulgakov once remarked "Remove the document and you remove the man." With its strict control of information the DPRK government under Kim Il-Sung could have very easily destroyed much of the documentary evidence on the abduction system once it became an international issue. Again, it is both reasonable and advisable to pressure the current DPRK leadership to do their utmost to produce evidence but expectations of complete satisfaction must be tempered by realistic appraisal of the problem. The current Japanese demands are that progress cannot be made until three goals are met: the return of all abductees (or their remains), a full accounting of abductees, and the handover of the perpetrators. Clearly a strict interpretation of these demands is unreasonable in that it may be impossible, regardless of what efforts are made, to fully satisfy them. Better targets would focus on evidence of progress taking place in the DPRK's investigation and resolution of the issue. Realistically this is all that can be expected and the rate of DPRK cooperation and transparency is only likely to increase with an easing of tensions between the two states (or, conversely, decline with any increase in tension and hostility). The abduc-

89) 'Japan Rejects Planned N. Korean Probe Report on Abductions', *Japan Economic Newswire*, 21 September 2014.

90) Sebastian Maslow, 'Will Japan and North Korea be Able to Solve the Abduction Issue?', *PacNet* No. 56, *CSIS*, 16 July 2014.

91) 'Japan Rejects Planned N. Korean Probe Report on Abductions', *Japan Economic Newswire*, 21 September 2014.

tion issue should not, therefore, be a prerequisite for better relations, but instead an element of fostering them. A significant and symbolic move on the DPRK's part would be to finally officially identify, and ideally hand over, some of those involved in the program. Gestures such as this, involving a certain element of compromise, can build an incremental path to a solution that hardline, irresolute demands will never achieve. In the past, positive negotiations on the issue have been derailed by changes in Japan's government,⁹²⁾ a factor which can put limits on the window of opportunity for substantial progress under any one leader. As of October 2014, according to the leader of the General Association of Korean Residents in Japan, the DPRK is making progress with its probe,⁹³⁾ and there is reason to hope that ongoing negotiations might act as a path toward a diplomatic détente. However, other factors could still derail the recent progress, one of them being opposition among Japan's allies to any easing of the sanctions in place against the DPRK. South Korea was shocked by Japan's rare unilateral action and expressed concern that it might compromise the international response to the DPRK's weapon development.⁹⁴⁾ The US own representative for DPRK policy, warned that the DPRK might be using the issue to drive a wedge between Japan and its allies,⁹⁵⁾ comments which highlight a significant split between the priorities of Japan and these states. While Japan is concerned over any military threat posed by the DPRK, for Seoul and Washington it is the primary issue. In Japan, however, the abduction issue is of far greater concern to the general public. While some academics have suggested that the impact will be negligible and that talks are likely to lead nowhere,⁹⁶⁾ they may in fact be a crucial turning point in Japan's relationships that directly confronts the question of what is more vital to Japan's security and regional growth, a focus on the DPRK as a military threat or recognition that a diplomatic path to rapprochement may be both more practical and more valuable. However, regardless of whether the latter might be in Japan's best interests, there will be strong pressure from Japan's allies to pursue the path of milita-

92) Atsuhito Isozaki, 'Japan North Korea relations: The Abe Administration and the Abduction Issue', *SERI Quarterly*, July 2013, 70

93) 'North Korea Making Progress in Abduction Probe – Partisan Official in Japan', *NHK*, 7 October 2014.

94) 'N.Korea-Japan Agreement Takes Seoul by Surprise', *Chosun Ilbo*, 30 May 2014.

95) 'Japan Mulls Talks with NKorea, Surprising Allies', *AP*, 22 May 2013.

96) 'N Korea Abduction Probe an Attempt to Divide Foes', *AFP*, 31 May 2014.

rized opposition to potential nuclear or missile threats and it remains to be seen whether Tokyo is capable of sustaining a truly independent foreign policy. Hideshi Takesada, a DPRK expert and Executive Director at the National Institute for Defense Studies, has said that certain groups or governments have already begun to utilize "disinformation tactics" by disseminating rumors designed to compromise Japan-DPRK negotiations.⁹⁷⁾ Japan thus has to juggle not only the problems of negotiation itself, but also domestic hardline anti-DPRK elements, media and academic perceptions that prioritize the military threat, and interference by its own allies. Successful resolution of this long-standing problem will offer Japan a solid platform from which to refocus its long-term regional strategy. A thaw in DPRK relations would lay the ground for reframing of the practical threat posed by the DPRK's military capabilities and a potential shift in Japanese perception of them from offensive to defensive systems. The display of independent foreign policy would also show states such as China and Russia that Japan is capable of formulating policy separate from that of Washington. Easing of sanctions and economic investment in DPRK would both boost Japan's economy and help stabilize the DPRK, alleviating the dangers of a sudden collapse and any resulting chaos. Increased diplomacy and economic growth would also act as tools through which significant human rights reform, aimed at the improvement of living conditions rather than regime change, might be encouraged within the DPRK.

CONCLUSION

Among the international community the DPRK is still seen as a rogue state. Other states to have been labelled as such include Iraq, Libya and Syria, and in each of these cases the use of military force was applied as a corrective tool of regime change with disastrous results. Even if the DPRK posed a tangible military threat there is little evidence to suggest that an aggressive military response would improve regional security or stability. In actuality, while it possesses offensive capabilities the DPRK offers no significant or pressing danger to any of its neighbors and has maintained its disproportionately large military out of its own fear of existential

97) Sebastian Maslow & Hiedshi Takesada: "Will Tokyo and Pyongyang be Able to Solve the Abduction Issue?" *Japan Foreign Correspondents Association*, 8 July 2014.

threats. The US intelligence community itself recognizes that the DPRK is “focused on deterrence and defense” and that its nuclear capabilities are tools of “deterrence, international prestige, and coercive diplomacy.”⁹⁸⁾ Increased military growth in surrounding states only serves to exacerbate both this siege mentality and the DPRK’s continued prioritization of spending on defense rather than the infrastructural needs of its people, a problem made far worse by the crippling economic sanctions it suffers.

This is not to suggest that the DPRK is a blameless victim. It has carried out a variety of illegal and provocative international acts, engaged in dangerous proliferation of nuclear, chemical and biological weapons, and is almost certainly guilty of widespread rights abuse. None of which negate the fact that proactive diplomacy, rather than paranoid military reactionism, is more likely to offer tangible returns in Japanese relations with the isolated state. It also offers the best chance Japan has of avoiding a collapse in the DPRK which could see other states fight over the scraps of the country and Japan’s own regional influence suffer. Such engagement would, regardless of whether or not DPRK nuclear weapons are tolerated, require a fundamental shift from viewing their weapon systems as offensive threats to Japan, and instead recognizing them as a necessary, if unwanted, defensive bulwark. This is not to say that such a path would unquestionably be the best strategic option for Japan but rather that a clear enough opportunity for reform exists, through continued easing of sanctions and support for DPRK economic development and regional integration, that it must be pursued as a legitimate strategic option. By doing this, and by establishing clear, and reasonable goal lines regarding the abduction issue, Japan can more effectively push for increased DPRK human rights reform and a higher degree of transparency. Such a task will be difficult, especially in the face of inevitable domestic and alliance opposition, yet less so than a fearful adherence to military and economic coercion or the advocacy of regime change, a strategy with a well-established track record of failure.

The potential returns are more than worth the effort involved: economic opportunities for Japan, increased respect as an independent force in international affairs, higher standards of living for North Koreans, and in-

98) James R. Clapper, *Worldwide Threat Assessment of the US Intelligence Community*, US Senate Select Committee on Intelligence, 29 January 2014, 6.

creased regional stability. The major potential cost would be a risk of backlash due to diverging from the regional objectives of the US, yet if the alliance does not offer Japan room to pursue the strategy most conducive to its long-term security then the fundamental benefit of the partnership must be reconsidered. The alternative would be to maintain the status quo: sanctions, military growth and increased security tensions with both the DPRK and, through this, China. Such a path will likely lead to an eventual collapse of the DPRK government and significant change in the regional balance of power. These two strategies of 'advancing stabilization' and 'promoting collapse' are inherently incompatible and Japan must determine which end result it intends to pursue. At present both options remain open, leaving Japan at a crossroads from which the choice of whether or not to further engage the DPRK will have considerable long-term implications for its future security and welfare.

The editorial board accepted this research note with reviews by referees on January 21, 2015.

